

**The prognosis of glutamic acid decarboxylase antibodies
in women with hyperglycemia in pregnancy**

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[Supplemental materials](#)

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Additional Figure 1: Flow chart

Additional Table 1: Metabolic characteristics and adverse pregnancy outcomes in women with GADA

measurement (study sample) or not (excluded from analyses)

	Women with no GADA measurement n=1,076	Study sample n=1,182	p-value
Glycemic status during pregnancy			< 0.01
Early-diagnosed gestational diabetes mellitus	193 (17.9%)	364 (30.8%)	
Gestational diabetes mellitus	827 (76.9%)	735 (62.2%)	
Diabetes in pregnancy	56 (5.2%)	83 (7.0%)	
Metabolic characteristics			
Age (years)	31.8 ± 5.5	32.8 ± 5.4	< 0.01
Pre-pregnancy body mass index (kg/m ²)	26.8 ± 5.5	27.4 ± 5.6	0.01
Family history of diabetes	342 (31.8%)	424 (35.9%)	0.04
Parity	2.24 ± 1.28	2.34 ± 1.29	0.1
Previous pregnancy(ies)			
<i>History of hyperglycemia in pregnancy</i>			0.40
First child	370 (34.4%)	364 (30.8%)	
No	551 (51.2%)	623 (52.7%)	
Yes	155 (14.4%)	195 (16.5%)	
<i>History of macrosomia</i>			0.50
First child	370 (34.4%)	364 (30.8%)	
No	643 (59.8%)	753 (63.7%)	
Yes	63 (5.9%)	65 (5.5%)	
<i>History of renal vascular diseases in pregnancy</i>			0.99
First pregnancy	251 (23.3%)	241 (20.4%)	
No	789 (73.3%)	900 (76.1%)	
Yes	36 (3.3%)	41 (3.5%)	
<i>History of fetal death</i>			0.94
First pregnancy	251 (23.3%)	241 (20.4%)	
No	794 (73.8%)	905 (76.6%)	
Yes	31 (2.9%)	36 (3.0%)	
<i>Ethnicity</i>			0.33
Sub-Saharan African	183 (17.0%)	182 (15.4%)	
North African	377 (35.0%)	431 (36.6%)	
Caribbean	42 (3.9%)	56 (4.7%)	
European	239 (22.2%)	228 (19.3%)	
Indian-Pakistan-Sri Lankan	159 (14.8%)	197 (16.7%)	
Other	76 (7.1%)	85 (7.2%)	
Maternal outcomes			
Caesarean section	267 (24.8%)	315 (26.6%)	0.3192
Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy	69 (6.4%)	79 (6.7%)	0.7950
Neonatal outcomes			
Large-for-gestational-age infant	170 (15.8%)	163 (13.8%)	0.1787
Small-for-gestational-age infant	89 (8.3%)	106 (9.0%)	0.5562
Preterm delivery (<37 weeks of gestation)	82 (7.6%)	76 (6.4%)	0.2678
Neonatal hypoglycemia	16 (1.6%)	22 (1.9%)	0.5995
Neonatal death and stillbirth	5 (0.5%)	2 (0.2%)	0.2686

Any malformation	17 (1.6%)	17 (1.4%)	0.7825
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Data are n (%) or mean \pm standard deviation

GADA: Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase antibodies

Additional Table 2: Metabolic characteristics according to three groups of GADA

	Available data	Negative GADA	Moderately positive GADA	Clearly positive GADA	Total	p-value
		n=1,095	n=56	n=31	n=1,182	
Screening for HIP before 22 WG						
Fasting plasma glucose (mmol/L)	n=773	5.2 ± 0.7	5.6 ± 1.8*	5.4 ± 0.9	5.2 ± 0.8	<0.01
Gestational age at HIP screening (WG)	n=778	12.15 ± 4.30	12.42 ± 3.87	10.91 ± 4.62	12.12 ± 4.29	0.38
Screening with OGTT at 22 WG or later						
Fasting plasma glucose (mmol/L)	n=832	5.1 ± 0.7	5.1 ± 0.7	5.5 ± 1*	5.1 ± 0.7	0.05
1-hour plasma glucose (mmol/L)	n=768	9.4 ± 2	9.4 ± 1.6	9.7 ± 2	1.712 ± 1.9	0.82
2-hour plasma glucose (mmol/L)	n=777	8.3 ± 1.9	8.7 ± 1.3	8.6 ± 1.6	8.3 ± 1.9	0.34
Gestational age at OGTT (WG)	n=833	27.25 ± 3.19	27.11 ± 2.66	26.13 ± 2.72	27.21 ± 3.15	0.27
Glycemic status during pregnancy						
	n=1,182					0.13
Early diagnosed gestational diabetes mellitus		339 (31.0%)	16 (28.6%)	9 (29.0%)	364 (30.8%)	
Gestational diabetes mellitus		684 (62.5%)	35 (62.5%)	16 (51.6%)	735 (62.2%)	
Diabetes in pregnancy		72 (6.6%)	5 (8.9%)	6 (19.4%)	83 (7.0%)	
Metabolic characteristics						
Age (years)	n=1,182	32.8 ± 5.4	33.6 ± 6.0	33.4 ± 6.0	32.8 ± 5.4	0.45
Pre-pregnancy body mass index (kg/m ²)	n=1,170	27.5 ± 5.6	26.2 ± 5.3	26.5 ± 4.7	27.4 ± 5.6	0.17
Pre-pregnancy obesity	n=1,170	339 (31.2%)	11 (20.4%)	9 (30.0%)	359 (30.7%)	0.24
Family history of diabetes	n=1,182	395 (36.1%)	14 (25.0%)	15 (48.4%)	424 (35.9%)	0.08
Employment at beginning of pregnancy	n=1,166	398 (36.8%)	20 (37.0%)	9 (29.0%)	427 (36.6%)	0.67
Parity	n=1,182	2.33 ± 1.27	2.43 ± 1.67	2.26 ± 1.24	2.34 ± 1.29	0.82
Smoking						
Before pregnancy	n=1,182	95 (8.7%)	2 (3.6%)	1 (3.2%)	98 (8.3%)	0.32
During pregnancy	n=1,182	52 (4.7%)	1 (1.8%)	1 (3.2%)	54 (4.6%)	0.76
Previous pregnancy(ies)						
History of HIP	n=1,182					0.23§
First child		328 (29.9%)	24 (42.1%)	14 (31.8%)	366 (30.6%)	
No		590 (53.8%)	22 (38.6%)	21 (47.7%)	633 (52.9%)	
Yes		178 (16.2%)	11 (19.3%)	9 (20.5%)	198 (16.5%)	
History of macrosomia	n=1,182					0.7§
First child		328 (30.0%)	23 (41.1%)	13 (41.9%)	364 (30.8%)	
No		707 (64.6%)	30 (53.6%)	16 (51.6%)	753 (63.7%)	
Yes		60 (5.5%)	3 (5.4%)	2 (6.5%)	65 (5.5%)	
History of renal vascular diseases in pregnancy						
First pregnancy	n=1,182	214 (19.5%)	15 (26.8%)	12 (38.7%)	241 (20.4%)	0.4§
No		844 (77.1%)	38 (67.9%)	18 (58.1%)	900 (76.1%)	

Yes		37 (3.4%)	3 (5.4%)	1 (3.2%)	41 (3.5%)	
History of fetal death	n=1,182					0.3§
First pregnancy		214 (19.5%)	15 (26.8%)	12 (38.7%)	241 (20.4%)	
No		845 (77.2%)	41 (73.2%)	19 (61.3%)	905 (76.6%)	
Yes		36 (3.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	36 (3.0%)	
Ethnicity	n=1,179					0.3
Sub-Saharan African		165 (15.1%)	11 (20.4%)	6 (19.4%)	182 (15.4%)	
North African		408 (37.3%)	12 (22.2%)	11 (35.5%)	431 (36.6%)	
Caribbean		50 (4.6%)	5 (9.3%)	1 (3.2%)	56 (4.7%)	
European		213 (19.5%)	9 (16.7%)	6 (19.4%)	228 (19.3%)	
Indian-Pakistan-Sri Lankan		182 (16.6%)	9 (16.7%)	6 (19.4%)	197 (16.7%)	
Other		76 (6.9%)	8 (14.8%)	1 (3.2%)	85 (7.2%)	

Data are n (%) or mean \pm standard deviation

GADA: Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase antibodies;

HIP: hyperglycemia in pregnancy; OGTT: oral glucose tolerance test; WG: weeks of gestation

*: vs negative GADA, symbol inserted only if significant ($p < 0.05$) after Dunnett adjustment for multiplicity

§: Yes vs No (no history possible if first child)

We considered that women with a GADA level < 1 UI/ml - the threshold for positivity according to the manufacturer - had negative GADA, that those with a level between 1 and 2.99 UI/ml had moderately positive GADA, and finally that those with a GADA ≥ 3.0 UI/ml had clearly positive GADA.

Additional Table 3: Biology according to three groups of GADA according to three groups of GADA

	Available data	Negative GADA	Moderately positive GADA	Clearly positive GADA	Total	p-value
		n=1,095	n=56	n=31	n=1,182	
Gestational weeks at measurement	n=1,181	28.4 ± 6.3	27.1 ± 5.6	27.0 ± 6.2	28.3 ± 6.3	0.17
Glycemic variables						
HbA1c (%)	n=1,012	5.2 ± 0.5	5.2 ± 0.5	5.4 ± 0.7	5.2 ± 0.5	0.07
Fructosamine (µmol/L)	n=1,129	200 ± 18	204 ± 19	215 ± 29*	200 ± 18	<0.01
Fasting plasma glucose (mmol/L)	n=1,168	4.6 ± 0.8	4.6 ± 0.8	4.9 ± 1.1	4.6 ± 0.8	0.18
Insulin (pM)	n=1,162	100 ± 68	91 ± 49	86 ± 50	99 ± 67	0.32
HOMA-IR	n=1,150	3.05 ± 2.452	2.77 ± 1.733	2.78 ± 1.956	3.03 ± 2.41	0.58
HOMA-B	n=1,098	342 ± 383	312 ± 320	288 ± 324	340 ± 379	0.64
Auto-immunity						
<i>Thyroid</i>						
TPOA (UI/ml)	n=1,178	23.9 ± 110.5	19.2 ± 62.5	19.1 ± 26.1	23.5 ± 107.3	0.92
Positive TPOA		75 (6.9%)	1 (1.8%)	3 (9.7%)	79 (6.7%)	0.2
<i>Diabetes</i>						
GADA (UI/ml)	n=1,182	0.14 ± 0.13	1.47 ± 0.56*	10.29 ± 15.04*	0.47 ± 2.9	<0.0001

Data are n (%) or mean (standard deviation)

GADA: Glutamic acid decarboxylase antibodies; HbA1c: glycated hemoglobin; HOMA-IR: homeostatic model assessment for insulin resistance; HOMA-B: homeostatic model assessment for insulin secretion; OGTT: oral glucose tolerance test; TPOA: thyroperoxidase antibodies; WG: weeks of gestation

*: vs negative GADA, symbol inserted only if significant (p<0.05) after Dunnett adjustment for multiplicity

We considered that women with a GADA level <1 UI/ml - the threshold for positivity according to the manufacturer - had negative GADA, that those with a level between 1 and 2.99 UI/ml had moderately positive GADA, and finally that those with a GADA ≥ 3.0 UI/ml had clearly positive GADA.

Additional Table 4: Adverse pregnancy outcomes according to three categories of GADA rates

	Available data	Negative GADA	Moderately positive GADA	Clearly positive GADA	Total	p-value
		n=1,095	n=56	n=31	n=1,182	
Maternal outcomes						
Gestational weight gain (kg)	n=1,105	9.5 ± 5.6	10.0 ± 5.0	9.5 ± 4.5	9.6 ± 5.5	0.85
Insulin therapy at the end of pregnancy	n=1,182	541 (49.4%)	28 (50.0%)	17 (54.8%)	586 (49.6%)	0.83
Insulin dosage at the end of pregnancy (UI/day)	n=541	25.7 ± 24.7	26.2 ± 25.1	35.3 ± 18.6	26.0 ± 24.6	0.33
Gestational age when insulin was started (weeks)	n=544	28.8 ± 6.5	27.7 ± 6.7	27.2 ± 6.3	28.7 ± 6.5	0.51
Caesarean section	n=1,182	299 (27.3%)	11 (19.6%)	5 (16.1%)	315 (26.6%)	0.18
Hypertension in pregnancy	n=1,182	36 (3.3%)	4 (7.1%)	2 (6.5%)	42 (3.6%)	0.11
Preeclampsia	n=1,182	34 (3.1%)	2 (3.6%)	1 (3.2%)	37 (3.1%)	0.77
Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy	n=1,182	70 (6.4%)	6 (10.7%)	3 (9.7%)	79 (6.7%)	0.23
Neonatal outcomes						
Small-for-gestational-age infant	n=1,182	94 (8.6%)	8 (14.0%)	5 (11.4%)	107 (8.9%)	0.26
Gestational age at birth (WG)	n=1,182	39.5 ± 1.6	39.4 ± 1.6	39.4 ± 1.5	39.5 ± 1.6	0.87
Preterm delivery (<37 WG)	n=1,182	70 (6.4%)	3 (5.4%)	3 (9.7%)	76 (6.4%)	0.67
Neonatal hypoglycemia	n=1,129	21 (2.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (3.3%)	22 (1.9%)	0.5
Neonatal death and stillbirth	n=1,182	2 (0.2%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (0.2%)	1
Any malformation	n=1,182	14 (1.3%)	3 (5.4%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (1.4%)	0.08

Data are n (%) or mean (standard deviation)

GADA: glutamic acid decarboxylase antibodies; WG: weeks of gestation

We considered that women with a GADA level <1 UI/ml - the threshold for positivity according to the manufacturer - had negative GADA, that those with a level between 1 and 2.99 UI/ml had moderately positive GADA, and finally that those with a GADA ≥ 3.0 UI/ml had clearly positive GADA

